

Query-by-Example Model Creation Methodology in Freesound

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*This work is dedicated to
all those who supported me
and continue to do so.
or not.*

You all have my deepest gratitude.

*There is an amazing amount of music that was never played.
What I'm seeking, is that.
This music that's in the air that is ready to played at all times,
you know?
That's why I show up at a concert.*

Keith Jarrett

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Abstract

In this thesis we investigate whether certain groups of features relate to the retrieval quality of Freesound. Freesound is an online collaborative audio database. People from different disciplines share their own audio materials under the different types of Creative Commons licenses. Freesound's similarity search functionality is one of the the features that is used by more users everyday. Freesound library is expanded everyday, as more users share their sounds, adding to the corpus of existing sounds. This expansion has brought to surface the need for a method that will be able to understand the similarity between sounds and retrieve the most relevant ones, given an example. For this reason, this problem can be classified in the Query-by-Example category.

We propose a modular model selection method that takes advantage of the readily available Freesound provided content and user provided context, attempts to select the most useful parts of it and increases the retrieval quality. Two different evaluation methodologies are employed, that provide a different type of scoring of the retrieved results. Because Freesound is an unstructured audio database, an experiment is designed and carried out that will serve as the ground truth for the these evaluation methods. Automatically judging the quality of the retrieved sounds, based on audio content and context similarity, holds promise for more accurate and contextually correct retrieval.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

1.1.1 Definitions of Similarity

The concept of Similarity has been extensively used among many different disciplines. In *Mathematics* and *Linear Algebra*, two matrices with the same eigenvalues are considered to be Similar [54]. In *Chemoinformatics*, the concept of Chemical Similarity holds an important role in the design of chemicals with specific properties [29]. In *Computational Linguistics*, where words and meanings are modeled as nodes and paths in graphs, graph based similarities have been used to reveal their relatedness [24]. In *Cognitive Psychology*, similarity principle is one of the Gestalt laws [58] and states that items with similar properties tend to be grouped [57] [9]. In *Information Retrieval*, where words of a document are mapped as points in a vector-space, similarity search is performed based on the number of the words they have in common. [36].

An attempt to capture the intuitive aspects of the concept of similarity was made in [55] and later in [32]. In this attempt, three basic intuitions capture the notion of a similarity measure. The only prerequisite is that the sole thing that relates the two objects being compared is the amount of similarities and differences they share. These intuitions are:

- The similarity between A and B is related to their commonality. The more commonality they share, the more similar they are.
- The similarity between A and B is related to the differences between them. The more differences they have the less similar they are.
- The maximum similarity between A and B is reached when A and B are identical, no matter how much commonality they share.

Under this perspective, the concept of similarity depends fully on the similarity measure used. Mathematically, while similarity measures adhere to the above intuitions, every similarity is created under different assumptions and thus every similarity measure provides a different type of similarity between two vectors. That should always be taken into account in model creation. With this basic intuitive notion of similarity in mind, we move on to how musical and audio signals are perceived in this context.

1.1.2 Similarity in Music Information Retrieval

Following the paradigm from Information Retrieval in documents, in Music Information Retrieval (*MIR*), information (features) extracted from the audio signal itself (content) and from metadata (context) is stacked in vectors. These vectors are then used by different similarity/distance functions to find how "similar" they are to each other.

Various similarity measures have been used in *MIR* (e.g. [5]), within the context of different models [7]. Usually, the input to a similarity measure is a vector or matrix of features that is of fixed length. Both objective and subjective similarity measures have been proposed [6], with the latter attempting to rectify the short-comings [16] of the former.

While research on similarity in *MIR* employs the use of Timbral [44], [2], Rhythm [20], Tempo [59] and Tonal features [22], these features remain manually selected. Rather, research has focused more on different models of existing descriptors (for example [52], [51], [1]) in order to approach more complex problems such as Cover Song Identification, Query-by-Humming, etc.

1.1.3 Audio Information Retrieval and the case of Freesound

Extending the work done in music, in Audio information retrieval, the same features are extracted from the audio signals and used in similarity search and retrieval in various contexts.

Currently in Freesound [15], similarity is done through a kNN search on feature vectors that are extracted from Principal Component Analysis of various statistics from all available lowlevel descriptors as they were extracted from Essentia [8]. This inhibits the understanding and usefulness of each feature. While research has been done [49] to find useful feature sets that classify well audio in the Gaver taxonomy, this work does not attempt to generalize to the rest of Freesound, which contains an even wider range of sounds. As the need for a taxonomy that contains the whole of Freesound was required, in [19] such a taxonomy was described. The general categories described are Effects, Instrument Samples, Soundscapes, Music, Voice/Speech.

This taxonomy will form the basis for this thesis' work. It will be used to categorize the sounds and therefore select the dataset that will be used. Even though, the methodology that will be described in the next section makes use of this specific taxonomy, it does not depend explicitly on the specifics of any given taxonomy or folksonomy, but only on their existence. It can be automatically modified to fit into any given taxonomy/folksonomy.

1.2 Goals

This dissertation is attempting to explore the ways to find a suitable model that is able to describe similarity in the way humans do and distinctly characterize audio categories (such as Music, Speech etc.). Furthermore, they will be evaluated in order to improve the accuracy and quality of the retrieves similarity results for queries done in Freesound. The methodology to reach these goals, is comprised by the following steps (with the algorithmic part also displayed in Figure 1.1);

1. Perform an experiment to obtain the ground truth.
2. Perform feature selection on features extracted from the audio signal.
3. Evaluate these methods against the ground truth.
4. Create a feature set from metadata containing tags and descriptions.

Figure 1.1: Flowchart of the methodology

5. Combine the best performing feature-set with context based extracted feature vectors.
6. Evaluate the performance in retrieval of the combined model.
7. Compare with the two previous feature sets.

1.3 Synopsis

In chapter two, the scientific background is described that provides information required to build the methodology that is introduced in chapter three. Results will be presented and discussed in chapter four. In chapter five, conclusions and suggestions for future work are highlighted.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Audio Information Retrieval

Research in Audio Information Retrieval stems from several fields such as *Environmental Sound Retrieval*, *Music Information Retrieval*, *Automatic Speech Recognition* and *Segmentation* [40]. *Environmental Sound Retrieval* includes all the types of sounds that are neither Music nor Speech. Because of the complexity of the sounds that exist besides Speech and Audio research is usually focused on specific types of sounds [49]. *Music Information Retrieval* has become a popular field with a lot of active research on different aspects of the challenges of MIR such as classification [44], issues that occur from modeling [16], incorporation of subjective similarity measures [7], cover song detection [51] and context based recommendation [19] being some examples. *Automatic Speech Recognition* focuses on the recognition of words in a syntactical level [48], later research has extended to extraction of emotion from speech [56] and language recognition [60]. These research fields are not disjoint, an example being [13], where Automatic Speech Recognition is used to align lyrics to a musical piece.

A fair amount of research efforts in various recognition and classification tasks has been done on the identification of the most important descriptors for a specific task [14], [25]. One of the popular descriptor-sets, due to its availability, is the one provided from MPEG7 [35]. Many of the included descriptors in MPEG7 are described by Peeters [46]. What changes, sometimes drastically, is the modeling of the descriptors into "higher order" ones, as will be described in the next subsections.

2.1.1 Environmental Audio

There has been a lot of work regarding Environmental Audio (soundscapes, sound effects) event recognition and classification, with the use of various different modeling approaches. Casey [11] employed the use of HMMs to recognize the state of an audio file. The descriptors they used were all in the context of MPEG7. Roma *et al* in [50] considered a specific feature set on a dataset and then applied SVM classification to distinguish different sounds to different categories. Following that, they segmented longer audio file and characterized the different sounds that existed in those segments. Aucouturier in [?] where by computing the MFCCs of every audio file and modeling them into a GMM model for every class by feeding all the MFCCs into a GMM. This final GMM model is then representing one audio class. By modeling in this manner, they are employing the use of the *bag-of-frames* where the sequence of events is irrelevant. After training, every new

audio file is modeled in that manner and classified according to its probability belonging to a specific class (how close its computed GMM model is to the class GMM model).

Heitolla et al in [26] created event classes (such as *coins/keys, applause*), trained HMM on MFCCs with the Expectation-Maximization algorithm and classified using the Viterbi algorithm. Moving a step forward they attempted to perform context recognition by searching for the most similar event in their database using the Cosine similarity. Later, Mesaros et al [38] combined content and context. They modeled content as GMM distributions of MFCCs and calculated the KL-Divergence to evaluate the distance between events. At the same time they modeled context by using path similarity derived as the inverse of the shortest path from the hierarchical conceptual classification of WordNet [39].

2.1.2 Music

In the field of Music similarity and classification, the work of *Aucouturier* [2] [3] [43] [4] has dominated the field. In this approach, frame based MFCCs are modeled into Gaussian Mixture Models of 2 normal distributions through the bag of frames method, building in that way a model that describes uniquely each song. This approach though has its pitfalls, as there does not exist an analytic form for the similarity measure they use (KL) for 2 Gaussians and approximate it through the use of MCMCs, something that slows down the process. Pampalk [?], used one Gaussian in the model and combined it with *Fluctuation Patterns*. They compute the KL divergence and the Euclidean metric separately for these two features and linearly combines them with weights.

Pohle et al in [47], extended the concept of bag of frames in a model called "*Rhythm-Timbre Bag of Frames*". They augment the MFCCs with the Harmonicness, Spectral Contrast and Attackness which are modeled as a covariance matrix for each song and are compared with the Jensen-Shannon divergence.

Seyerlehner et al [53] creates another similar approach, *Block Level Similarity* where by computing the Spectral Pattern, Delta Spectral Pattern, Variance Delta Spectral Pattern, Fluctuation Pattern, Correlation Pattern and Spectral Contrast Pattern with each fitted to its own model and compared with the Manhattan metric. They normalize the distances and linearly combines them with weights and renormalizes. This method performs similarly to Pohle's approach (RTBOF), but when they linearly combines them (and renormalizes), they yield better performance when compared to each one separately.

2.1.3 Instrument Samples

As in music, a lot of research has occurred in automatic instrument recognition [27]. Descriptors relevant to perceptual and taxonomic categorizations of sounds have been proposed, such as "brightness", "attack" [23] or MFCCs or the ConstantQ transform. As a further example, [37] tested 31 features in an attempt to classify 14 orchestral and wind instruments. The most useful ones were vibrato and tremolo strength and frequency, onset harmonic skew (i.e., the time difference of the harmonics to arise in the attack portion) centroid related measures (e.g., average, variance, ratio along note segments, modulation) onset duration, and select pitch related measures (e.g., value, variance).

2.1.4 Voice

In the field of speech recognition/characterization research was already underway in the early '80s but it is still ongoing. One of the most significant works was Laver's [31], where he studied the physiological correlation with different voicing modes (breathy, creaky, modal, voiceless, etc).

Figure 2.1: The components of a content based audio retrieval system [40]

2.2 Features

2.2.1 Content

In this section we will make a rundown of the features that are extracted from the audio files with Essentia [8], and are then stored and compared in the Gaia server [42], where similarity search takes place. These algorithms are presented in Table 2.1. Along with the actual descriptors, their following statistics are computed, presented in Table 2.2. Because of the amount of

descriptors, the reader is referred to the Algorithm Overview¹ and Reference² on the Essentia website for complete explanations of the outputs of the algorithms. Additionally, for the complete and analytical list of descriptors that are used in Freesound the reader is referred to the Freesound Documentation³.

Spectral	Time-Domain	Tonal	SFX
BarkBands	Duration	HPCP	LogAttackTime
MelBands	Effective Duration	Tun. Frequency	TCToTotal
ERBBands	ZCR	Key	MaxToTotal
MFCC	Leq	Chords Det.	MinToTotal
GFCC	LARM	Chords Descr.	PitchSalience
LPC	Loudness		
HFC	LoudnessVicker	Rhythm	
SpectralContrast		Beats Loudness	
Inharmonicity		BPM	
Panning		First & Sec Peaks	

Table 2.1: Descriptors used in Freesound

Mean	Energy
GeometricMean	RMS
PowerMean	InstantPower
Median	
Single Gaussian	Central Moments
Variance	Raw Moments
Skewness	Crest
Kurtosis	
Flatness	1st Derivative
Max	2nd Derivative
Min	

Table 2.2: Statistics computed in Freesound

2.2.2 Context

Metadata (or Context) is structured information that describes, explains, locates, or otherwise makes it easier to retrieve, use or manage an information resource. Metadata is often called data about data or information about information [28]. Metadata can be rich and expressive so there are many scenarios where this approach is sufficient [12]. Metadata can be curated by a group of experts or generated by users (social metadata).

Context based data are different by the content based data in that they are able to capture aspects of audio that are beyond the audio signal, such as activities related to a song, tags that

¹Essentia Algorithm Overview

²Essentia Algorithm Reference

³Freesound API Docs

describe the audio in cultural and perceptual terms. There is no need for the audio file in order to generate this kind of information as they are usually user based. One major problem of the context based descriptors is their dependence on the availability of sources. This means that without the existence of web pages that describe in metadata (or tags) there would be no information. One solution to that problem is the creation of databases maintained from expert users, but that has been proven to be expensive and not fast enough to catch up to the current speeds of album releases per day. Going one step further, communities of users could maintain these databases and freely tag audio files (songs or otherwise), but due to cultural differences noise would infiltrate the signals.

2.3 Freesound

Freesound [41] is a collaborative database of audio files. People from all around the world, coming from different disciplines and with a different purpose in mind share their audio files, under a selection of Creative Commons Licenses that allow their reuse. Audio content includes, but is not limited to, instrument samples, speech, audio loops, soundscapes and synthesized sounds, etc.

The initial goal of Freesound was to give researchers access to a common database of royalty free audio as well as the ability to artists to use prerecorded samples in their song creation process. Since then, a highly active community has been built around it, which contributes to its function in various different ways beyond uploading (moderating, commenting, etc.) [18]. Its size has surpassed 200,000 audio samples and this number steadily increases.

In order to further engage researchers and developers, in 2011 an API was introduced that allowed browsing the site essentially through any http client. This includes searching through simple queries, filtering sounds through their context and/ or content properties and targeting specific audio descriptors. This has become possible with the use of MTG's inhouse creations, Essentia⁴[8] for feature extraction and Gaia⁵ for similarity search. The workflow of Freesound that combines all these technologies together is presented in Figure 2.2 [17]. Version 2 of the API is at the moment in beta stage and is soon to be released and will provide many new features such as improved search options (e.g. combined search of content and context and upload of new sounds⁶).

Similarity search remains a standing issue regarding *both* content and context. It is not uncommon when searching sounds that are similar based on content to a given audio example to retrieve sounds that are perceptually irrelevant. Furthermore, it is also not uncommon to search for a tag and retrieve (again) an irrelevant sound due to the noise embedded in the user tagging process, something that, among others, displays the cultural differences among the users of Freesound. One more source of error is the restrictions that are imposed on Freesound by the several different technologies that are being used. As an example, Gaia attempts to find similar sounds by using the Euclidean metric on the averages of all the descriptors of the two sounds.

While context based analysis is underway and its performance is being improved upon [19] and content based analysis is an issue being addressed [50], it is yet not optimized to its full potential. The main question being, "*which features describe certain qualities of a sound that can*

⁴Essentia Website

⁵Gaia Website

⁶Freesound API v2

Figure 2.2: Freesound architecture

determine their similarity in some perceptual sense?".

2.4 Feature Selection and Extraction

2.4.1 Content Feature Selection

Feature Selection is a step often overlooked, where a bulk of available descriptors is computed and used in order to perform similarity search and classification. It is one of the most important processes in the modeling of the feature representation as it is the only way to provide to the similarity search or classification algorithm with the most relevant information about the task involved.

Manual Selection of features corresponds to hand-crafting a set of features that will be applicable to the involved task. Most of the feature extractors have been created with a very specific task in mind, tonality and rhythm being two immediate examples. This feature set is then evaluated to decide whether the intended aspect of audio is well represented in the feature space. This approach has been given the name *knowledge engineering* [10]. Following this process, specific Machine Learning procedures (such as PCA) are applied to the features in order to decorrelate them and extract an even more relevant feature set [50].

Another approach that makes use of supervised machine learning is the automatic induction of relevant feature sets when a ground truth exists. This kind of approach allows for the selection of relevant feature sets without the need that the algorithm designers reason or guess on their selection. An even more sophisticated approach has been followed by Makinen [34] [33] and Kiranyaz [30] which uses Multi-Dimensional Particle Swarm Optimization, and attempts to not only find the feature set from the initial features, but synthesize its own features in the process. While this is an automated feature separator, it has been deemed slow and the synthesized

features do not contain a direct meaning towards humans.

In this dissertation all the available descriptors are taken into account and processed for their usefulness via two different standardized feature selection processes. The processes are *Extremely Randomized Trees* [21] and *Univariate feature selection via Select K-Best* Methods.

The first algorithm, *Extremely Randomized Trees* is used to compute feature importances, which in turn can be used to discard irrelevant features. What differentiates this algorithm from tree based ones is that it splits nodes by choosing cut-points fully at random and that it uses the whole learning sample (rather than a bootstrap replica) to grow the trees [21].

The second algorithm, *Select K-Best*, performs the χ^2 statistical test to features. The χ^2 measures how independent of the current classification task a specific feature is, thus setting it with a low score. In this manner, only the features more relevant to the task at hand are easily identified and the K Best performing features are kept.

2.4.2 Context Feature Extraction

One of the most prominent measures in Natural Language Processing is the Term Frequency - Inverse Document Frequency *TF-IDF* measure. The *Term Frequency* is equal to the times a term occurs in a document. *Inverse Document Frequency* is the inverse of the number of documents that contain the specific term. Every document is a point in the vector space of terms. For more information the reader is directed to the sixth chapter of [36].

2.4.3 Dataset

The quality of the training dataset is crucial and has to be defined in terms of a taxonomy. To construct the dataset, we need to consider at least two different aspects: the number of categories and the number of instances per category. In this thesis the dataset that was used in [19] will be used. Font et al in [19] attempt to create a taxonomy (presented in Figure 2.3) that is able to contain the whole of Freesound and at the same time is in-line with previously proposed taxonomies, such as the one proposed in [11]. The sound categories are:

- Effects (FX)
- Instrument Samples
- Soundscapes
- Music
- Speech/Voice

The dataset comprises of more than 20000 sounds that have been manually labeled in [19], with each class containing from 2088 to 6341 sounds. The classes are not exclusively mutual, as there are a lot of sounds that may fall under two categories. One example being a Soundscape of a city street that contains Speech (these sounds should fall into the Speech category) at one moment and some musicians playing music (these sounds should belong to the Music category).

Figure 2.3: Font et al proposed taxonomy of Freesound Audio Sounds

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Dataset Creation

The dataset used in this dissertation is a subset of the manually annotated dataset from [19]. For every audio category, 24 representative and distinct sounds were gathered, making up a total of 120 sounds. Some example sounds are shown in Figures 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5. All content based audio descriptors were collected in the format provided by Freesound (means, vars, means of derivatives, vars of derivatives, etc) as well as all the context (tags and descriptions) for each sound.

3.2 Content Based Feature Selection

In order to perform feature selection, all M features from the content descriptors are vectorized in a matrix of size $N \times M$, where N is the number of sounds in the dataset and M is the number of features. All the feature values are normalized so as to take values from $[0, 1]$. This matrix is then used as an input to the two feature selection algorithms.

Each of the Feature selection Algorithms is run multiple times on the original feature matrix. The first **5, 10, 20, 30, 50, 100** features were kept in turn. The resulting feature-sets were then used to create a symmetric similarity matrix using the *Cosine Similarity*. Their performance against the user created symmetric similarity matrix is evaluated and one of the 12 resulting feature-sets is selected to be combined with the context based vectors.

Figure 3.1: Examples of FX sounds

Figure 3.2: Examples of Instrument Sample Sounds

Figure 3.3: Examples of Soundscape Sounds

3.3 Context based Feature Extraction

3.3.1 Tags

All the tags are retrieved from their corresponding sound. Vectorization of the vocabulary was done with the *TF-IDF Vectorizer* from the popular *Python* machine learning oriented library *scikit-learn* [45]. English stop-words were removed. Also, Words with TF-IDF values outside $[.05, .99]$ were discarded. In Figure 3.6 only tags from metadata are used to create the resulting vectorspace.

Since the resulting vectorspace from these operations is usually very high, especially when dealing with bigger datasets, the resulting dictionary is transformed with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) into 30 dimensions.

3.3.2 Tags and Descriptions

The configuration of the *TF-IDF Vectorizer* was the same as before, English stop-words were removed and words with TF-IDF values outside $[.05, .99]$ were discarded. Following this transformation, PCA was used in order to reduce the dimensionality to 30.

Similarity matrices with the use of the *Cosine Similarity* are depicted in figures 3.6 and 3.7, in order to show the initial differences of the two different resulting vector spaces (tags only and the tags and descriptions).

The two resulting matrices of size 120×30 each, are evaluated both on their similarity and differences between them and the user created matrix created from the conducted experiment.

3.4 Combining Content and Context

Having obtained the best possible content and context feature-sets, they are combined creating an composite feature matrix.

Figure 3.4: Examples of Music Sounds

Figure 3.5: Examples of Speech/Voice Sounds

The linear combination of the feature selection step and the context extraction will be presented. The linear combination

$$\mathbf{S} = \alpha \cdot \mathbf{CNT} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \mathbf{CTX}$$

with **CNT** representing the content vectors, **CTX** representing the context vectors and scalar α , with $1 \geq \alpha \geq 0$, representing the mixing proportions of the two matrices. This formula provides a conceptual way that these are united. The content feature matrix is multiplied by the scalar value of $(1 - \alpha)$ and the context similarity is multiplied by α . Thus the feature vectors are scaled *before* being transformed into the similarity matrix. The value of $\alpha = .5$ will be used in this thesis.

3.5 Evaluation

Evaluating in an objective manner is a non trivial task. In order for it to have any meaning, it requires a concrete definition of the ground truth.

For this reason an experiment was devised, where users had to listen to two different sounds and rate their similarity from a scale of zero to ten. The experiment was conducted online and was constructed with Django¹. Subjects' ages range from 22-60 and from no musical training to fully trained professional musicians. Every subject was allowed to complete as many questionnaires as they wanted, given that they did not complete one questionnaire more than once and did not fatigue themselves in the process. In the course of one week, approximately 11500 comparisons were collected, covering the initial need of 7140 replies and giving more certainty to approximately half of the comparisons. The Landing page and user interface for the experiment are presented in Figures 3.8 and 3.9 respectively.

The first evaluation comes from [5] and involves the comparison of the ordering of two similarity matrices. One serves as the ground truth and the other as the query similarity matrix. Each matrix row is sorted in decreasing similarity and treated as the result of a query for a corresponding target sound. The top 'N' hits from the ground truth matrix are assigned exponentially-decaying weights so that the top hit has weight 1, the second weight α_r , the next α_r^2 , etc, with $\alpha_r < 1$. The candidate similarity matrix 'query' is scored by summing the weights of the hits by another exponentially decaying factor, so that a ground truth hit placed at rank r is scaled by α_c^{r-1} . Thus this "top-N ranking agreement score" s_i for row i is:

$$s_i = \sum_{r=1}^N \alpha_r^{r-1} \alpha_c^{k_r-1}$$

where k_r is the ranking according to the query measure of the r^{th} -ranked hit under the ground truth α_r and α_c govern how sensitive the metric is to ordering under the query and ground truth

¹The Django Project

Figure 3.6: Similarity matrix created by the use of tags

Figure 3.7: Similarity matrix created by the use of tags and descriptions

measures respectively. In this thesis $\alpha_r = .5$ and $\alpha_c = \alpha_r^2$. Finally, the overall score S is the average of the normalized row scores.

$$S = \frac{1}{N} \sum_1^N \frac{s_i}{s_{max}}$$

where s_{max} the maximum of all row score values.

The second evaluation is adapted from the MIREX evaluation. Since in the current dataset there does not exist the effect of the artist. For every run, the following objective Statistics derived from the similarity/distance matrix:

- Average % of Category matches in the top 5, 10, 20 & 50 results (Precision)
- Average % of available Category matches in the top 5, 10, 20 & 50 results (Recall)
- % File never similar (never in a top 5, 10, 20 & 50 result list)
- Plot of the "number of times similar curve" - plot of song number vs. number of times it appeared in a top 20 list with songs sorted according to number times it appeared in a top 20 list (to produce the curve). Systems with a sharp rise at the end of this plot have "hubs", while a long 'zero' tail shows many never similar results.

The similarity matrix generated from the experiment is presented in Figure 3.10. This similarity matrix will serve as our ground truth in evaluating the content feature selection, context feature extraction and their combination.

Figure 3.8: Welcome page and questionnaire selection for the user similarity rating experiment

Figure 3.9: An example questionnaire for the user similarity rating experiment

Figure 3.10: User Generated Similarity Matrix. Each vertical red line denotes a category change.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Content

4.1.1 Extremely Random Trees

First the Extremely Random Trees Feature Selection algorithm results will be presented and evaluated with the user generated similarity matrix in Figure 3.10.

		Number of Returned queries							
		5		10		20		50	
		Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.
Num. of Feat.	5	0.4689	0.5467	0.4365	0.575	0.3645	0.6571	0.291	0.7303
	10	0.4892	0.5317	0.4543	0.56	0.355	0.6562	0.2922	0.7278
	20	0.5075	0.4983	0.4521	0.5617	0.3719	0.6375	0.3008	0.7227
	30	0.4529	0.5583	0.4135	0.6017	0.3831	0.6312	0.2835	0.7338
	50	0.4555	0.5617	0.4435	0.5667	0.3709	0.6413	0.2952	0.7262
	100	0.4878	0.5433	0.4425	0.5733	0.3659	0.6496	0.2798	0.74

Table 4.1: Average precision and recall for the Extremely Random Trees Feature Selection Method

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	5	0.0917	0.0250	0.0167	0.0083
	10	0.1250	0.0583	0.0167	0.0083
	20	0.1167	0.0417	0.0167	0.0083
	30	0.0750	0.0417	0.0167	0.0083
	50	0.1417	0.0333	0.0083	0.0083
	100	0.1000	0.0417	0.0167	0.0083

Table 4.2: Percent of Files Never Similar with the Extremely Random Trees Feature Selection Method

Figure 4.1: The similarity matrix create from a feature-set selected from Extremely Random Trees Feature Selection Algorithm (the red vertical lines help separate one category of sounds from another)

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	5	0.2255	0.2409	0.2544	0.2603
	10	0.2143	0.2410	0.2737	0.2480
	20	0.2166	0.2443	0.2463	0.2506
	30	0.2346	0.2531	0.2746	0.2465
	50	0.2301	0.2529	0.2519	0.2603
	100	0.2181	0.2522	0.2394	0.2583

Table 4.3: Evaluation of the Extremely Random Trees Feature Selection Method with the Logan et al Measure

Figure 4.2: The *Always/Never Similar* curves for the feature-sets extracted from Extremely Random Trees Feature Selection Algorithm

4.1.2 Select K Best

Next the Select K Best Feature Selection algorithm results will be presented and evaluated with the user generated similarity matrix in Figure 3.10.

Figure 4.3: The similarity matrix created from a feature-set selected from Select K-Best Feature Selection Algorithm (the red vertical lines help separate one category of sounds from another)

Figure 4.4: The *Always/Never Similar* curves for the feature-sets extracted from Select K-Best Algorithm

		Number of Returned queries							
		5		10		20		50	
		Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.
Num. of Feat.	5	0.3698	0.6250	0.3570	0.6367	0.3176	0.6767	0.2594	0.7385
	10	0.4441	0.5583	0.3990	0.6067	0.3519	0.6621	0.2755	0.7325
	20	0.4355	0.5967	0.3838	0.6475	0.3425	0.6833	0.2698	0.7503
	30	0.4468	0.5933	0.3961	0.6325	0.3492	0.6721	0.2781	0.7373
	50	0.3856	0.6367	0.3685	0.6525	0.3292	0.6858	0.2689	0.7495
	100	0.4274	0.5983	0.3762	0.6483	0.3312	0.6892	0.2561	0.7622

Table 4.4: Average precision and recall for the Select K-Best feature-set Selection Method

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	5	0.0250	0.0083	0.0083	0.0083
	10	0.0417	0.0250	0.0083	0.0083
	20	0.0667	0.0167	0.0167	0.0083
	30	0.1000	0.0417	0.0333	0.0250
	50	0.1000	0.0667	0.0333	0.0333
	100	0.1500	0.0667	0.0333	0.0250

Table 4.5: Percent of Files Never Similar with the Select K-Best Feature Feature Selection Method

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	5	0.1099	0.1234	0.1321	0.1325
	10	0.1020	0.1096	0.1150	0.1154
	20	0.0942	0.1057	0.1114	0.1119
	30	0.1313	0.1466	0.1530	0.1534
	50	0.1096	0.1224	0.1316	0.1320
	100	0.1111	0.1299	0.1379	0.1382

Table 4.6: Evaluation of the Select K-Best Feature Feature Selection Method with the Logan et al Measure

4.2 Context

4.2.1 Tags

In this subsection the Tags similarity matrix is evaluated first.

Figure 4.5: The similarity matrix created from the Tags extracted feature set

		Number of Returned queries							
		5		10		20		50	
		Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.
Num. of Feat.	30	0.5656	0.4350	0.5283	0.4708	0.4353	0.5675	0.2844	0.7218

Table 4.7: Average precision and recall for the Tag extracted feature-set

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	30	0.0083	0.0083	0.0000	0.0000

Table 4.8: Percent of Files Never Similar with the Tags extracted feature-set

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	30	0.1861	0.2120	0.2206	0.2210

Table 4.9: Evaluation of the Tag extracted feature-set with the Logan et al Measure

Figure 4.6: The *Always/Never Similar* curves for the feature-sets extracted from the Use of Tags

4.2.2 Tags & Descriptions

In this subsection the Tags & Descriptions similarity matrix is evaluated.

Figure 4.7: The similarity matrix created from the Tags and Descriptions feature set

		Number of Returned queries							
		5		10		20		50	
		Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.
Num. of Feat.	30	0.5146	0.4833	0.4740	0.5250	0.4172	0.5821	0.2895	0.7175

Table 4.10: Average precision and recall for the Tag & Description extracted feature-set

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	30	0.0167	0.0083	0.0083	0.0000

Table 4.11: Percent of Files Never Similar with the Tag & Description extracted feature-set

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	30	0.1827	0.2076	0.2115	0.2119

Table 4.12: Evaluation of the Tag & Description extracted feature-set with the Logan et al Measure

Figure 4.8: The *Always/Never Similar* curves for the feature-sets extracted from the use of Tags & Descriptions

Figure 4.9: Similarity Matrix of the Combined SKBest Content Feature Set and the Tags Feature Set

4.3 Combining Context & Content

The feature set that resulted from the SKBest algorithm with a number of 5 features is selected from the Content based Feature Selection Process. It was selected because of its more robust 'scaling up' behavior when more features are selected. Precision drops less than the rest feature set sizes and recall increases. Additionally, it provides a fairly small amount of hubbs.

4.3.1 SKBest and Tags

Figure 4.10: The similarity matrix created from the combined SKBest and Tags feature-set

		Number of Returned queries							
		5		10		20		50	
		Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.
Num. of Feat.	35	0.5868	0.4350	0.5261	0.5	0.4399	0.5891	0.2949	0.7225

Table 4.13: Average precision and recall for the Tag extracted feature-set

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	35	0.0250	0.0083	0.0000	0.0000

Table 4.14: Percent of Files Never Similar with the Tags extracted feature-set

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	35	0.2323	0.2587	0.2652	0.2655

Table 4.15: Evaluation of the Tag extracted feature-set with the Logan et al Measure

Figure 4.11: The *Always/Never Similar* curves for the feature-sets extracted from the Use of Tags

4.3.2 SKBest with Tags & Descriptions

Finally, the combined SKBest with Tags & Descriptions feature set is evaluated against the user similarity matrix.

Figure 4.12: The similarity matrix created from the combined SKBest and Tags & Descriptions feature set

Figure 4.13: The *Always/Never Similar* curves for the SKB and Tags & Descriptions combined feature sets

		Number of Returned queries							
		5		10		20		50	
		Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.	Prec.	Rec.
Num. of Feat.	35	0.5531	0.4550	0.5192	0.4983	0.4428	0.5679	0.3061	0.704

Table 4.16: Average precision and recall for the Tags & Descriptions extracted feature-set

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	35	0.0166	0.0083	0.0083	0.0000

Table 4.17: Percent of Files Never Similar with the Tags & Descriptions extracted feature-set

		Num. of Queries			
		5	10	20	50
Num. of Feat.	35	0.2040	0.2293	0.2344	0.2347

Table 4.18: Evaluation of the Tags & Descriptions extracted feature-set with the Logan et al Measure

Chapter 5

Conclusions & Future Work

5.1 Conclusions

The Select K Best feature selection method, required a very small amount of features to prove robust and without having a particular 'hubness' problem, as was the case with the Extremely Random Trees feature selection algorithm. In addition, the Extremely Random Trees, because of its randomized behavior did not provide consistent results at all times, despite the fact that the results were averages of 100 runs of the algorithm.

The combination of information extracted directly from the audio signal and information extracted from metadata positively increased both the retrieval quality and quantity, based on the proposed evaluation methods. The use of descriptions in the context feature matrix, resulted in less precision, but better recall. At the same time, the use of descriptions in the context feature space reduced the 'hubs' a fair amount, compared to the use of only tags to populate the context feature space.

Lastly, this thesis' approach is meant to be used more as a proof of concept than a precise description of a model. The way to combine the different parts in order to create a model for a given AIR task is more important than the current tools for feature selection, extraction and evaluation.

5.2 Contributions

The main contributions of this thesis can be summarized as:

- The use of descriptions to complement the use of tags in the context based feature extraction. The results are positive in that descriptions help reduce the 'hubness' of, at least, the dataset used in this thesis.
- The use of feature selection in an unsupervised manner to select the best available feature set. The result is a very compact feature set that comprises of a minimum of content features that is not able to perform as well, but has a positive impact when used in conjunction with the Context feature set.
- The creation of a modular model selection method. The methodology described here can be used with any other feature selection/extraction method for a lot of similarity/classification tasks in Audio Information Retrieval.

5.3 Future Work & Extensions

In particular main improvements and extensions of the present study are:

- The systematic development of a larger corpus that can serve as a ground truth as well as continuous evaluation. The dataset used in this thesis is very small compared the actual content available in the Freesound database. A simple continuous evaluation of the retrieval results can be applied on whether users find them similar/relevant to the actual content they were expecting.
- The incorporation of more feature selection techniques. The techniques presented in this thesis are rather simple. Feature selection techniques created with Audio Information Retrieval can be devised that can be more effective in feature selection process.
- Incorporation of the WordNet taxonomy between tags. Distance of tags (and descriptions) could be derived as the distance of shortest path on the hierarchical taxonomy of WordNet. Such a technique could help reduce some of the noise inherent to tags and descriptions.
- Comparison of more similarity measures. This can help reveal different facets of similarity that cannot be captured with the cosine similarity measure that was used in this thesis.
- More elaborate evaluation measures are required. By employing more elaborate evaluation methods, different facets of similarity can be evaluated and, thus, suggested systems would be able to emulate user similarity more faithfully.

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